

The Roles of South Sudanese Women Entrepreneurs in Small Business Development and Sustainability

AUTHOR(S): CHOL GABRIEL MAJER

Abstract

The overall goal of the study is to assess the roles of south Sudanese women entrepreneurs in small business development and sustainability and women are willing to take action in business and contribute to the nation's economic growth. The study employed a sample size of 35 respondents. The respondents were selected using a simple random sampling method and purposive sampling. In this study, questionnaires and interviews were employed as the primary data gathering tool. The data gathered in the field was analyzed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 16.0, which included descriptive statistics like percentages as well as inferential statistics like frequencies percentages analyses. The objective of this paper is to investigate to study the available support services of south Sudanese women entrepreneurs in juba, to explore the constraints and challenges faced by women entrepreneurs to suggest some policy recommendations to overcome these constraints, to study the government cooperation on the women entrepreneurs development program in south Sudan, to study the SWOT analysis of south Sudanese women entrepreneurs in south Sudan. The research used a qualitative and quantitative research design using in-depth interviews and focus groups. The findings were that the challenges were identified as impediments to south Sudanese women business entrepreneurs, which comprises lack of education and training, lack of access to finance, gender discrimination, negative attitudes and inadequate resources. Recommendations were made to south Sudanese women entrepreneurs, to the government of South Sudan and other stakeholders. The research, therefore, recommends that attention there is need for regular seminars, conferences and workshops for the owners of the small business among the women entrepreneurs in order for the region to experience rapid and sustainable economic transformation desired in South Sudan market.

IJARBAS

Accepted 22 September 2021
Published 27 September 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5532840

Keywords: South Sudan, Business Management, Innovation, Women Entrepreneurs, Women Entrepreneurship, Challenges,

About Author

Author(s):

CHOL GABRIEL MAJER,

MBA (Generic), PGDBA, BBA Opt Banking & Fin,
DIP Banking & Fin.,
South Sudan.

E-mail: cholgabrielmajer83@gmail.com

1. Introduction

The research aim is to look at the roles play by South Sudanese women entrepreneurs in small business development and sustainability for better economy growth of South Sudan. In view of the need to bring the South Sudan women entrepreneurs in the development stream of the nation, the South Sudan Government, the NGOs and other UN agencies had provided business opportunities to promote entrepreneurial skill among South Sudanese women entrepreneurs. The income-generating activities, credit facilities, skill training, market opportunities have all combined to open up the ways for the business entrepreneurial development among south Sudanese women in Juba and whole of South Sudan. Since 2010, over 100 million women in 59 countries (52% of the world's population) started and grew a new enterprise according to (Kelly et al., 2011). The role of South Sudan women entrepreneurs in small business development and sustainability is regarded as South Sudan women empowerment in Business development it is a way or process that enables South Sudanese women to gain access to and control over the physical resources as well as nation building. It is a mechanism of awareness and capacity building leading to greater participation in the decision making process according to (M.A. Awwal Sarker, 2006). Around the Africa women's empowerment has recently gained considerable importance as an area for policy and policy interventions in most of the organizations of Africa. They have recognized the benefits of the empowerment that can be achieved through effective participation of women in Business activities. And of course, promotion of entrepreneurship plays a vital role in empowering the womenfolk. In the South Sudan economy, Women owned businesses are the fastest force, prompting women business owners 'the new face of economy. This research is based on the roles play by South Sudanese women entrepreneurs in Juba through entrepreneurship development. There is no denying the fact those developing countries particular in Africa are reclining under the brunt of acute shortage of CapitalLand alarming problems of underemployment. Small Business entrepreneurs with their built attributes of low capital intensiveness and enormous employment generation potential can serve as propelling agents to break the vicious circle of poverty and can strike the engine of economic development (Srivastva, 1994).

Practically, South Sudan women brings motivation, they have a vision which is different, realistic, modern and enthusiastic. When civil society and social structures leave them on possibility for evolving their careers, women take their own initiative. They are quite naturally drawn to initiative, to creation and to management of businesses. So, promoting women's empowerment through skill and entrepreneurship the government of any developing country can ensure freedom of choice and a better quality of social living for men and women. However, about 52 percent of the populations of South Sudan are in absolute or moderate poverty and about 76percent of them live in rural areas (Mohiuddin; Moniruzzaman; Mahmud, 1998). Here, about 50% of the total populations (140.0 million) are women, according to the 2001 census. South Sudanese women's participation in business was conspicuously insignificant for a very long period because there was little opportunity for women to participate in genuine decision making at any level or in any area of life. However, there has been a rise in the number of South Sudanese women entrepreneurs starting small business in the developed and developing countries in recent years since a new generation of highly educated and motivated women is emerging, and they are creating businesses through their own choice.

In East Africa women are increasingly entering into the field of entrepreneurship by starting small venture. As mentioned earlier, such a trend is also observed among the women

community in South Sudan. Here, the approach of women's empowerment through entrepreneurship development is gaining momentum since women have become aware of their existence, their rights and work situation and their power. A few numbers of studies on the role of women have focused on various areas such as women's role in family, polity, and national wealth, and generation, legal and social rights of women (Jahan, 1995; Adnan, 1993; Barakat, 1994; Islam, 1994). From the angle of women empowerment through development, some findings of these studies will be helpful to guide the nation for future direction; especially to identify the areas where active intervention is required. The classical and neo-classical theorists have labored in trying to define entrepreneurship, but this has not resulted in a single definition of entrepreneurship. It all depends on the focus of the one defining it and from which perspective one looks at it. Entrepreneurship is a multidimensional concept. Most recent research defines entrepreneurs as a venture that involves a nexus of two phenomena: the presence of lucrative opportunities and the presence of "enterprising individuals" (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000).

1.2. Statement of the Problem.

Today although South Sudanese women entrepreneurs significantly contribute to the success of an economy in various nations of the world, there are various challenges that hinder their entrepreneurial progress. According to Agbenyegah (2013), entrepreneurial activities in South Sudan have shown gradual decline over the years compared to other developing countries. Luiz and Mariotti (2011) state that Africa has consistently ranked very poorly in the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor survey in terms of entrepreneurial activity. It is clear that South Sudan is not producing a sufficiently entrepreneurial economy and this need to be addressed so as to create employment, expand markets, increase production and revitalize communities (Luiz & Mariotti 2011). Entrepreneurs are faced with many obstacles that limit their growth and survival (Nyamwanza, Mapetere, Mavhiki & Dzingirai 2012). In addition to this, women have to cope with negative prevailing social and cultural attitudes, lack of education and training, as well as gender discrimination (Akhawaya & Havenga 2012). Although though the small business sector within the Juba City opportunities for existing entrepreneurs and for new venture creation, the question arises as to what barriers, problems, challenges and constraints women entrepreneurs encounter within the Juba City. The reason for the study is to explore the problems facing women entrepreneurs within the selected areas of the Juba City of South Sudan and additionally this paper will advance the understanding of the barriers faced by women entrepreneurs within the Juba city of South Sudan. The study will also look for possible solutions to minimize these challenges in the micro enterprises. The objectives of this paper are to explore the problems that women entrepreneurs face in their day to day activities, to come up with solutions to the problems that women entrepreneurs are encountering, to explore the areas in which Government and the private sector can intervene to assist women entrepreneurs with regards to the problems and to suggest practical recommendations of how to alleviate challenges faced by South Sudanese women entrepreneurs in the Juba City of South Sudan.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

To study the available support services of South Sudanese women entrepreneurs in Juba, to explore the constraints and challenges faced by women entrepreneurs, to suggest some policy recommendations to overcome these constraints, to find out if there were government policies, statutory or customary laws that make access to resources difficult for women entrepreneurs and to study the SWOT Analysis of South Sudanese Women Entrepreneurs in South Sudan.

1.3. Scope of the Study.

In Juba City South Sudan there are a huge number of small business enterprises owned by in Juba markets and that is why the respondents can easily be got.

2.0. REVIEW OF LITERATURE.

The researches on core entrepreneurship principally focusing on the male entrepreneur come to the limelight in the 1930s. The late 1970s led to the emergence of a specific sub domain of entrepreneurship (Hughes, Jennings, Brush, Carter, & Welter, 2012).

South Sudanese Women Entrepreneurs: Although South Sudanese women entrepreneurs have become important players in the entrepreneurial landscape, it is imperative to clarify what are women entrepreneurs. Iyiola and Azuh (2014) define a woman entrepreneur as a female who plays a captivating part by repeatedly interacting and keenly adjusting herself with financial, socioeconomic, and support spheres in society. According to Manerkar (2015), women entrepreneurs may be defined as the women or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. Women entrepreneurs start, own, operate, manage and take risks in their business (Thuaiba Azlah, Rozeyta, Hisyamuddin & Noorizwan2007). From the authors' definitions of a woman entrepreneur it can be concluded that a woman entrepreneur is the female front-runner of a business who takes the initiative of introducing a new venture, who accepts the associated risks and who is effectively responsible of its day-to-day activities. The most common aspects in the definitions is that South Sudanese women are involved in the operation and running of the business.

Women Entrepreneurship: Since entrepreneurship is both a complex and controversial concept, in order to comprehend the concept of women entrepreneurship it is imperative to start by noting or observing what entrepreneurship means. According to Chinomona, Maziriri and Moloji (2014) entrepreneurship is defined as the act of initiating, creating, building, expanding and sustaining a venture, building an entrepreneurial team, and gathering the necessary resources to exploit an opportunity in the marketplace for long-term wealth and capital gain. From the authors' definition, it can be seen that entrepreneurship is a capacity and willingness to develop, organize and manage a business venture in order to make a profit. Arakeri (2006:2) points out that women entrepreneurship comprises of an enterprise owned and controlled by a woman and having a minimum financial interest of 51 percent of the capital and giving at least 51% of the employment generated in the enterprise to women. From the definitions given it is possible to conclude and appreciate that women entrepreneurship is the process whereby an individual, develops a new venture or business unit. This can include an entrepreneurial individual acquiring an existing business or firm that is owned and controlled by a South Sudanese woman. Women in action in this paper merely mean women have been enlightened economically to be active in business but there are still some challenges that they face (Iyiola & Azulu 2014).

Innovation: In today's business competitive global environment an entrepreneur's ability to introduce innovations is a key success factor for sustaining competitive advantage. In an increasingly interconnected world, national economies face stiff competition for markets, resources and skills. Consumers in turn are more demanding of originality and innovation (Heckman 2000). Similarly, Dess, Lumpkin and Fisher (2007) describe innovation as using new techniques to transform organizational processes or create commercially viable products and services. In simpler terms, innovation is the process of making improvements by introducing something new. Price, Stoica and Boncella (2013) define innovation as a process that begins with an invention, proceeds with the development of the invention, and

results in the introduction of a new product, process or service to the marketplace. It has been described as the successful implementation of creative ideas, which can lead to solutions to problems that can have a potential impact on revenues of a firm, industry sector effectiveness, and the prosperity of nations (Price, Stoica and Boncella, 2013). Therefore, from the authors' definitions of innovation, it can be concluded that to be innovative indicates the ability to be creative, having successful use of an idea that adds value to the customer and commercial return for the creator and lastly, innovation is the process that renews something that exist or the birth of something new.

The Challenges faced by South Sudanese Women Entrepreneurs in Juba marketing/sales skills

Lack of Education and Training: Running a business is very risky for any entrepreneur, even more so for women entrepreneurs who not only have to survive in a male-dominated environment but also often lack the education and training in this field (Phillips, Moos & Nieman 2014). According to Ascher (2012), many women in developing countries remain illiterate and live in poor communities. Matiwane (2005) states that South Sudanese women entrepreneurs are ill-equipped educationally and financially. In a study conducted by Orford, Wood, Fischer, Herrington and Segal (2003) on the main obstacles faced by several Women entrepreneurship, the results of which indicated that the most recurrent weakness is lack of education and training among entrepreneurs. According to Jalbert (2000) for the South Sudanese woman entrepreneur, the process of operating a business can be very difficult in both the formal and informal sector because she often lacks the skills and education. Based on these authors' elucidations, it is clear that many South Sudanese women Entrepreneurs lack training and education, which create problems for women in the setting up and running of business enterprises.

Limited or No Access to Finance: O'Neil and Viljoen, (2001) point out that the most crucial of these barriers is finance. Finance is regarded as "life blood" for any enterprise, is it big or small (Singh 2012:51). Wasilczuk and Zieba (2008: 160) believe that financial barriers are one of the most important obstacles women have to face when setting up and developing a business. Phillips, Moos & Nieman (2014) point out that women entrepreneurs in South Africa have been particularly disadvantaged in the past as they do not own any property, which can be used as collateral on loans and need their husbands' permission to enter into financial arrangements. It is clear that women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital and they are not able to acquire external financial assistance due to the absence of tangible security and credit in the market (Phillips et al. 2014). Additional another challenge faced by south Sudanese women entrepreneurs did not have access to finance for setting up their business.

Access to financial institutions: South Sudanese women entrepreneurs face considerable hardships in accessing finance. Because, they are outside the radar of formal financial institutions, despite several Government instructions to open up for the marginal clients.

Lack of awareness of facilities and support services: Women entrepreneurs in rural area are unaware of available support services and the procedures for getting it. Mechanisms for disseminating information on investment opportunities and the types and sources of assistance available are inadequate (Karim, 2001).

Lack of institutional support facilities: Different institutions in South Sudan are characterized by corruption, large-scale inefficiencies, lack of initiative, and ineffective

decision-making (ADB 1997). Banks, furthermore, are not structured in such a way as to reach a target clientele without capital or assets (Karim, 1995).

Lack of social capital: Due to lack of social capital, poor people at the rural area do not have the social networks and this deprives the target groups of a key linkage with business partners which could otherwise have provided valuable assistance regarding different aspects of business development.

Inadequate management and marketing/sales skills: Lack of proper management and marketing/sales skills is an apparent issue for the young people. In case of problems related to management skill twenty respondents responded significantly major, fifteen responded major, twelve responded minor, two responded significantly minor and one responded not a problem. The result is almost same in the issue of marketing/ sales experience.

3. Methodology.

This chapter focused on research methodology sampling area, research design, study sample and sampling strategies. The area of study, focused of the study, population, sample size and sampling techniques, population, sample size, sampling techniques, simple random sampling, sample selection, methods of data collection, instrument, questionnaire, interviews, data analysis plan, data collection procedure, data analysis and interpretation, documentary review, procedure of data collection, data collection methods and techniques, data analysis, quantitative data analysis, qualitative data analysis, ethical considerations and chapter summary was use to achieve the objective of the study. The information was computerized and processed using SPSS computer software and Microsoft excel. Tables and graphs (Bar graphs) were highly presented, narrative notes were used to explain the information summarized in tables frequencies and percentages the data was then coded and fed into a computer program (The Statistical Package SPSS and Microsoft excel) for easy analysis and interpretation of results. Primary data were analyzed through descriptive statistics, Frequency analysis was used to analyze the primary data using the SPSS software and Microsoft excel.

- ✓ Legal assistance includes transparent regulation for getting Trade license etc. as well as other processes
- ✓ Financing helps to reduce interest rate, easy access to loan, and Guarantor free loan for South Sudanese women entrepreneurs
- ✓ Marketing assistance should be built among people to use local products and market should be created abroad through fair and other promotional campaigns
- ✓ Technology includes continuous product/service quality control, quality enhancement through adopting new technology, tax reduction on imported new machinery etc.
- ✓ The Business management includes a range of activities like HR, employee handling, customer and management, record keeping, costing, inventory management, procurement, strategic positioning and so on.

4. Data presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

4.1. Data Analysis Methods

After the fieldwork before analysis, all the questionnaires were adequately checked for completeness. The information was coded and entered into a spread sheet and analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences and micro soft excel). The data was checked to ensure that the output was free from outliers and the effect of missing responses was at the minimum. Quantitative analysis involved generating descriptive statistics. The descriptive statistics included frequency tallies, and their corresponding percentage scores. The findings were presented by using tables and graphs as found appropriate. Qualitative analysis

involved categorizing of data from interviews and field notes into common themes and presented using frequency distribution tables and graphs. Analysis and Discussion of Data in analyzing the data, the study revealed that the roles of South Sudanese Women Entrepreneurs in Small Business Development and Sustainability improve economic growth.

Table- 1 Type of Income Generating Activities in South Sudan

Income Generating activities	Frequency	Percent
Fruit and Vegetable sellers	4	11.4
Handicrafts and second hand clothes	6	17.1
Tailoring Business	7	20.0
Fish sellers	4	11.4
Restaurants Business and fruit Juice	11	31.4
Cow ; Milk sellers	3	8.6
Total	35	100.0

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2021

Table 1 above indicated that income generating activities carried out by business women in Juba markets were as follows Fruit and Vegetable sellers where 11.4%. Handicrafts and second hand clothes 17.1% Tailoring Business 20.0% Fish sellers 11.4% Restaurants Business and fruit Juice 31.4% Cow; Milk sellers 8.65. The studies concluded that income generating Activities in South Sudan led to improvement of small business and development and live sustainability.

Graph Showing: Income Generating Activities in South Sudan

Table 2: "Type of business"

Manufacturing	Trading	Services
Handicrafts	Cloth item	Beauty parlor
Embroidery	Flower business	Education service
Boutique	Wholesale business	Event management (Wedding, seminar, etc.)
Catering	Retail Business	IT Service (internet café)
Toy making		Research consultancies and Training

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2021

The above table 2 analysis shown that “Type of business” operate by business women in Juba Markets were as follows Manufacturing for business Handicrafts, Embroidery Boutique, Catering and Toy making and Trading include Cloth item, Flower business, Wholesale business and Retail Business and Services Beauty Parlor Education service, Event management (Wedding, seminar, etc.), IT Service (internet café) and Research consultancies and Training.

Graph 3: South Sudanese Women Income Generating Activities

Table 4: The Sources of South Sudan Women Entrepreneurs Business in Juba City

Bank loan	Self finance
Loan from financial institutions	Family
Other persons	Friend
Any combination of the above options	Other institutions

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2021

Table 4: The Sources of South Sudan Women Entrepreneurs Business in Juba City Markets Bank loan, Loan from financial institutions, other persons, any combination of the above options self finance, Family, Friend and Other institutions.

Table 5: Problems faced by South Sudanese Women Entrepreneurs

Significantly Major	Major	Minor	Significantly minor	Not a problem	Total Respondents
Start-up finance	33	2	0	0	35
Finance for Working Capital	23	4	8	0	35
Trust among suppliers and customers	27	4	2	0	35
Management skill	20	10	1	4	35
Marketing/ Sales skill	19	4	3	7	35
Access to markets	0	2	18	9	35
Access to technology	0	3	26	6	35

Infrastructural problem (Water, electricity, gas, transportation, etc.)	17	14	4	0	0	35
Family support	20	6	3	1	5	35
Access to business support	0	0	2	4	29	35
Political unrest	4	23	5	3	0	35
Policy area (difficult legal requirements and bureaucratic procedures)	4	7	21	3	0	35
Gender discrimination	12	3	3	0	17	35

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2021

Graph Showing: Problems faced by South Sudanese Women Entrepreneurs

SWOT Analysis:

The SWOT Analyses of the South Sudanese women entrepreneurs’ development state Policy and Business Environment.

Strength.

- ❖ South Sudan Women entrepreneur can be defined as a confident, innovative and creative South Sudan woman capable of achieving self economic independence individually or in collaboration, generate employment opportunities for others through initiating, establishing and running the enterprise by keeping pace with her personal, family and social life.
- ❖ South Sudan Women prefer to work from their own residence, difficulty in getting suitable jobs and desire for social recognition motivates them self-employment.
- ❖ Cheap labor, natural resources and Material-technical and financial support of the international NGOs and South Sudan Government financial institution.

Weaknesses.

- ❖ Absence of proper support, cooperation and back-up for South Sudanese women entrepreneurs by their own family members and the outside family people force them to drop the idea of excelling in the Business enterprise field.
- ❖ South Sudan Women's family obligations also bar them from becoming successful entrepreneurs in the markets
- ❖ High level of black market or economy, inadequate level of business education and information advisory service from business and management consultancy firms
- ❖ Inaccessibility of credit resources and undevelopment of financial market
- ❖ Economical instability, Lack of sound market competition in the market
- ❖ Heavy taxation burden imposed by Revenue Authority on and complicated account.

Opportunity.

- ❖ South Sudanese Women inculcate entrepreneurial values and involve greatly in business dealings
- ❖ Business opportunities that are approaching for South Sudan women entrepreneurs are eco- friendly technology, Bio-technology, IT enabled enterprises, event management, tourist industry, Telecommunication, Plastic materials, Mineral water, Herbal & health care, Food, fruits and vegetables processing.
- ❖ South Sudan Women entrepreneurs avail new opportunities in the rural areas such as Ice cream, channel products, and pickles and readymade garments.

Threats.

- ❖ Fear of expansion and Lack of access to technology
- ❖ Lack of self-confidence, will power, strong mental outlook and optimistic attitude amongst women creates a fear from committing mistakes while doing their piece of work.
- ❖ Credit discrimination and Non Cooperative officials.
- ❖ Insecure and poor infrastructure and Dealing with male labors.
- ❖ Instable energy supply from Mombasa port in Kenya, Bad defends of economic borders of Uganda Kenya Sudan and DR Congo, unsettled regional conflicts, Disintegrated regional markets, Political instability, Lack of protection of the inner market from the illegal and adulterated products, Unfavorable investment environment.

Summary of Findings

An analysis of South Sudan Government policy documents revealed that policies were developed under the assumption that South Sudan women entrepreneur's access to resources. Based on assumption, the criteria for access includes conditions such as detailed project documentation, high and select collateral, long-term customer relationships, business location, advanced degrees and high equity contribution. These requirements are based on the assumption that South Sudanese women have resources to hire experts to prepare detailed feasibility studies; are highly educated, owned titled land in have been able to establish long-term relationships with financial institutions to have enough resources to contribute the required level of equity. These criteria indicated that South Sudanese women have equal access to land, buildings, education, and possess the freedom, finances, and time to carry out business in Juba Markets. But in South Sudan, women are still less likely to own land and other assets, and they are less educated compare male. Fulfilling requirements, therefore, is challenging for women. This is despite the reality that South Sudan women comprise the majority of Small business operators and small businesses form the bulk of the enterprises in South Sudan. Moreover, the analysis of the literature shows that the

Government credit program's average loan has risen to levels beyond the reach of small business. This increase in loan size, combined with the bank's shift in focus from small business sector to curing, proves increasingly challenging for women who are primarily involved in small business activities.

Recommendations

The Government of South Sudan and UN agencies i.e. Non-Governmental organizations (NGOs) should open training South Sudanese women entrepreneurs according to their needs and want. Finance should be made available to enable women entrepreneurs to access business development and other services. The South Sudanese Society and the community at large should be made aware of the needs of South Sudanese women entrepreneurs and more specifically those with in adequate knowledge, skills and the skilled ones. General Public should be aware of their valuable contribution so that they might be more friendly and supportive towards South Sudanese women entrepreneurs who are operating their business in Juba City.

Provide training: on gender integration for business associations with which donor organizations and its implementing partners work. The training should focus on the importance of analyzing gender issues related to their activities to better understand and therefore address the needs of both male and female members and effectiveness of investments.

Policy Environment: the improvement of the policy environment for enhancing South Sudanese women's entrepreneurship, by adopting measures on the practical experiences and policy lessons-which should be shared women entrepreneurs and disseminated with adequate international and multilateral support.

There is need to install a spirit of entrepreneurship in Juba city, especially among South Sudanese women. A lot needs to be done to have efficient and effective education, which results in global competitiveness. Universities alone cannot do the change in terms of grooming South Sudan women entrepreneurs; it requires participatory approach from all angles. High quality education and high standards and relevance of education can lead to institutions of higher learning having quality graduates who can be employable and have a sustainable advantage everywhere. The current study is an attempt to undertake a research in an often neglected area but yet an important sector of the South Sudan businesses. The findings of this paper is to provide fruitful implications across all stakeholders in South Sudan's tertiary institutions to put more emphasis on entrepreneurship as it brings money to the Government, provides employment and alleviation of poverty, for women in particular. All stakeholders need to be involved in decision-making, including the parents, for efficacy to be realized and change how people view South Sudanese women entrepreneurs. But there is need to provide adequate resources for this dream of uplifting South Sudanese women entrepreneurship to be realized. Kayamba (2007) asserts that government policy-makers in South Sudan have put in place programmes to improve the situation of women in business. Therefore, it is imperative for South Sudanese women entrepreneurs living in the Juba City South Sudan to be aware of entrepreneurial support schemes, which are organized by the Government of South Sudan; for example, the South Sudan Micro Finance, Promotion Agency and the Small Enterprise Development Agency. It is best for the South Sudan Government to focus on providing equipment and developing infrastructure to support women entrepreneurs for better business operation activities. The South Sudan Government should struggle to improve intellectual capacity building among women entrepreneurs on entrepreneurship education by expanding and strengthening tertiary education. Verheul, Van

Stel and Thurik (2004) are of the view that the Government can provide female entrepreneurs with special loans, subsidies, funds, enterprise centre, entrepreneurship awards, counseling, training, advisory support, information products and web portals.

Therefore, South Sudan Government should come up with a considerable dedicated fund especially for South Sudanese women entrepreneurs in order to support their entrepreneurial small business activities.

The other recommendations was that South Sudanese Women entrepreneurs should raise confidence, empower themselves through entrepreneurial education, which is one of the initiatives that can be designed to enhance skills and knowledge in entrepreneurship. It is recommended that women entrepreneurs should acquire skills that will help to break the stereotypes and value systems that hinder them from participating in everyday activities. South Sudanese Women entrepreneurs should form partnerships with individuals from different areas of knowledge and expertise in order to learn from one another. It is also recommended that South Sudanese women entrepreneurs should acquire business skills training that will help to break the stereotypes and value systems that hinder them from participating in everyday activities. Women entrepreneurs should form partnerships with individuals from different areas of knowledge and expertise in order to learn from one another.

Conclusion.

This study has examined the key words, namely South Sudanese women entrepreneurship, innovation, South Sudanese women entrepreneurs, challenges; juba city South Sudan Many authors have tried to define these most important concepts differently. For positive change to be realized around these aspects there is need for all people to come together and have an input to ensure that all views are included in decision making for South Sudan women empowerment. It is important to note that students, especially women, should be afforded opportunities and resources to make decisions and learn about entrepreneurship. The greatest challenge facing entrepreneurs in the Juba is lack of resources. There is need for South Sudan Government to allocate more financial resources to women entrepreneurs especially that still at the introductory stage. South Sudan Government should allocate more funds to micro businesses operated by women because financial problems is one of the greatest issue that is affecting South Sudanese women to be in action in terms of entrepreneurship.

The researcher's professional involvement with women entrepreneurs faced with discrimination and sexism from their male counterparts and society at large. also, discrimination exist among both private and Government financial institution in Juba, but obtaining investment from family members and friends can provide an avenue to capital that may be more beneficial in terms of access and repayment. Additionally, there is a negative perception relating to the ability of South Sudanese women-owned small businesses to provide goods and services in competitive market However, this is slowly evolving toward a more positive concept. It will be some time before the negativism is eliminated. Fourth, the economic growth and potential being experienced in the city Juba will provide business opportunities for the next few years. Juba women entrepreneurs need to study local growth industries and be ready to take advantage of these opportunities.

Also there is no Government initiative to promote and support innovations among South Sudanese women-owned businesses. on business training, is crucial to the survival of the interviewees' businesses. The entrepreneurial innovations of the women in this research study, which are manifested in the operations of small businesses, have been a major factor

that influenced their survival. Although other elements contributed to their survival as reported in the study, their propensity to innovate, through the acquisition of raw materials, product development, production processes, and marketing stands out the most significant factor that influences the survival of their small businesses in Juba City Market. Therefore, this investigation has answered the following stated research question: What factor has the influence on the roles of South Sudanese women-owned small businesses in Juba city markets.

Limitations and Future Research

In spite of the contributions of this research paper, which provide avenues for future researches first and most significantly, the present research is conducted from the entrepreneurs in Juba City South Sudan Perhaps if data collection is expanded to include other towns, findings might be more insightful. The research was also conducted in urban areas only, future research might focus on both urban and rural areas. There is also the problem of common method bias because both quantitative and qualitative research was used in this study. It would have been more robust if the study included both qualitative and quantitative methods. All in all, these suggested future avenues of study stand to contribute new knowledge and skills to the existing body of South Sudanese's women small business entrepreneurship literature, a context that happens to be fewer studies by researchers in Sub-Saharan Africa.

REFERENCES

- Ascher, J. (2012). *Female Entrepreneurship – An Appropriate Response to Gender Discrimination*. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Innovation*. 8(4) 97-114.
- Kelly, DJ, CG Brush, PG Greene and Y Litovsky (2011). *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2010 Women's report*. (www.gemconsortium.org/docs/download/768). Mohiuddin, Muhammad;
- Kelly, DJ, CG Brush, PG Greene and Y Litovsky (2011). *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2010 a women's report*. [www.gemconsortium.org/docs/download/768].
- Matiwane, M. (2005). *South African Women entrepreneurship: A burgeoning force in our economy*. A special report for SAWEN, an initiative of the DTI group.
- Moniruzzaman; Mahmood, Muhammad Monowar Hossain. (1988). *Women Entrepreneurship Development in Rural Areas: A Case Study in Rural Areas: A Case Study On BSCIC Funded Enterprises*. *Dhaka University Journal of Business Studies* Vol.19 (1), P.45-63.
- O'Neil, R.C. & Viljoen, L. (2001). *Support for Female Entrepreneurs in South Africa. Improvement or decline?* *Journal of Family Ecology and Consumer Sciences*. (29) 37-44.
- Orford, J., Wood, E., Fischer, C., Herrington, M., & Segal, N. (2003). *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor: South African Executive Report*, Cape Town: University of Cape Town, South Africa.
- Orford, J., Wood, E., Fischer, C., Herrington, M., & Segal, N. (2003). *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor: South African Executive Report*, Cape Town: University of Cape Town, South Africa.

- Phillips, M. Moos, M & Nieman, G. (2014). *The Impact of Government Support Initiatives on the Growth of a Female Business in Tshwane South Africa*. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences. 5(15) 85-92.
- Phillips, M. Moos, M & Nieman, G. (2014). *The Impact of Government Support Initiatives on the Growth of Female Businesses in Tshwane South Africa*. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences. 5(15) 8592.
- Phillips, M. Moos, M & Nieman, G. (2014). *The Impact of Government Support Initiatives on the Growth of Female Businesses in Tshwane South Africa*. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences. 5(15) 8592.
- Singh, R. (2012). *Women entrepreneurship issues, challenges and empowerment through self help groups: an overview of Himachal Pradesh*. International Journal of Democratic and Development Studies, 1(1) 45-58.
- Sinha, S. (2005). *Developing women entrepreneurs in South Asia: Issues, Initiatives and Experiences UN ESCAP: Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific*. Women entrepreneurs in developing countries. [Online] Available: pdf file [Accessed: 3 April 2015].
- Srivastava, R.M. (1994): "*Emerging Profile of Small Women Entrepreneurs Cum Managers in India*", A Case Study of Women Management – Champions of Change, Khair Jahan Sogra, (ED), University Press Limited, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- Wasilczlik, J. & Zieba, K. (2008). *Female entrepreneurship in transitional economies: the case of Poland*. Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship, 21(2) 153-170.

Cite this article:

Author(s), CHOL GABRIEL MAJER, (2021). "The Roles of South Sudanese Women Entrepreneurs in Small Business Development and Sustainability". **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 19- 33 **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5532840> , Issue: 9, Vol.: 3, Article: 3, Month: September, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

